

MODERN CONCEPTS OF STATE ADMINISTRATION IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT In this article, the role and importance of foreign experience in culture and art education in our country, the attention paid to this field in our country, the formation and development of culture and art education, and the need to use foreign experience in this field. The reforms are analytically described. It also provides information on the adaptation of art and culture management to the conditions of Uzbekistan, the study of the activities of all art institutions in our Republic based on new creativity in management, and the recommendations that help it. In addition, the attention paid to the sphere of culture and art in the modernizing Uzbekistan, the measures implemented and planned to be implemented in the future were discussed.

Key words: art, culture, management, practice, theory, society, production, development, height, awakening.

INTRODUCTION In 2017, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated at the meeting with the leaders of culture and art: "We should never forget one fact: if culture and art do not develop in our country, society will not develop. The level of development of our people is evaluated primarily according to our national culture. In this sense, culture is the image of our nation and society. As we are starting to create a new image of Uzbekistan, we should start with the development of our national culture. Here, let's consider the analysis of foreign experience. Official websites, online platforms of Goldsmith University of Great Britain, Appalachian State University of the United States of America, Japanese University of Culture and Arts, the name of the relevant course, how to start the study, its duration, the number of students, the exam "teaching areas, levels of educational specialists, methods of monitoring and controlling the educational process, types of the educational process, criteria for evaluating the educational process, the content and duration of the educational process were studied in depth.

MAIN PART: The work carried out in our country for the development of culture and art is extremely consistent with the priority measures aimed at ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level reflected in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan. We can say that these reforms will contribute to the practical realization of the idea "From the strategy of actions - to the strategy of development" based on the principle of goodness and humanity, to the realization of the concept of "New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society". Each nation occupies a strong place in world civilization with the power of its culture and art. The development of this sector is one of the important factors that show the strength and potential of the country, the value of the people, its reputation and status in the world.

Currently, in the newly developed "Strategy of Development", a separate section is allocated to the spiritual and educational sphere and the inclusion of a work plan in the sphere of culture and art during 2022-2026 is an example of high attention directed to the sphere. . For

us, spirituality is a complex of exemplary qualities, mutual trust, respect and attention between people, noble aspirations to jointly build the future of the nation and the state. In other words, spirituality is the foundation that determines the content and quality of all political and social relations in society. Above, we have given a number of examples of the high level of attention and care paid to the industry today. Extensive work is being carried out within the framework of measures for the development of such a field, as well as high attention and ensuring the execution of signed decrees and decisions. It would not be wrong to say that the care and opportunities given to the industry by the head of our state will lead to radical changes in the near future and will bear fruit. Feeling such high attention and trust, young experts and industry workers like us should work more enthusiastically and mobilize all their strength and potential for the development of culture and art. Therefore, as the Honorable President noted, "New Uzbekistan will become a strong, potential, well-respected, prosperous and prosperous country in the world."

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Cultural Activities and Cultural Organizations" adopted by the Legislative Chamber and approved by the Senate on January 6, 2021 regulates cultural activities, relations in the field of cultural organizations, the creator, the creative community, is extremely important in terms of supporting creative activity. Public cultural events in our country, concerts and performances, folk art, folk games, activities of cultural centers, national cultural centers, strengthening cooperation in the field of cultural activities, promotion of cultural objects and works of art, development of culture in remote areas, social protection of cultural workers is considered. As an example of the high attention paid to the field and its representatives, we can see that April 15 is designated as the "Day of Culture Workers". It is not an exaggeration to say that on the eve of this joyful day, the establishment of the "Artists' Garden" at Nurabad Fortress, the educational center of Ohangaron district of Tashkent region, on the initiative of the Ministry of Culture, was like a wedding. This reality, which had never been observed before, pleased the industry workers immensely. This historical reality was welcomed and cheered by industry workers. It is not wrong to say that it motivated them to fulfill their duties more seriously. The above-mentioned Presidential Decree No. PQ-112 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" involves attracting young people to cultural centers, holding contests, festivals, set priorities such as identifying talented young people, supporting creative young people, increasing the level of providing cultural recreation services to the population, especially citizens living in remote areas.

CONCLUSION Culture and art management means managing processes and personnel in culture and art institutions. As the world becomes globalized, people are increasingly interested in the culture of the peoples of the world. People's enthusiasm for all fields and types of art and the growing demand for consumption are gaining importance.

References:

1. Decree No. PF-6000 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 26, 2020 "On measures to further increase the role and influence of the sphere of culture and art in the life of society".
2. Decision PQ-3391 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 17, 2017 "On measures to further develop the art of Uzbek national status".

3. Decision PQ-3656 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2018 "On the holding of the international status art conference".
4. Decision PQ3880 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 24, 2018 "On additional measures for the development of the national film industry".
5. Decision PQ-3920 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 26, 2018 "On measures for the innovative development of the sphere of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan".

